

DSPICE: New Software for Modeling Analog Elements and Circuit Simulation Using SPICE

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Abstract:

All technology instruments use electrical and electronic systems that, before their production, need to be verified via simulation software. A new simulation software called DSPICE (Designing Circuits and Simulation by SPICE) has been programmed. As presented in this paper, the main objective of this software is to simplify the modeling of analog elements and circuits to describe design schematics involving libraries, packages, and symbols. DSPICE would be a free software (GNU license). The circuit simulation in DSPICE allows a detailed frequency-domain analysis, DC analysis, and time-domain analysis. The output signals are acquired in different operating points and they are displayed by means of a dedicated waveform editor. The behavioral modeling of analog elements and the simulations results of different test circuits are reported in the text.

Keywords Ngspice, DSPICE, Circuits, CAD, python

1. Introduction

New software called DSPICE (Designing Circuits and Simulation by SPICE) [1]. With the rapid development of devices technology, the design of electrical circuits is becoming more and more computer-dependent. The circuit outputs cannot be determined by manual calculations which lead to a high probability of error and are too many time consuming. The increasing complexity of circuits makes the use of Computer Aided Design (CAD) tool an advanced methodology playing a key role in this field. Nowadays, for example, Spice is largely used by designers [2]-[3]. In fact, after more than four decades of operation with different generations of computers in simulating critical problems in highly complex circuits, Spice is considered the best circuit simulator around the world. Also, Spice inspires different commercial and free electronic design automation (EDA) programs, such as Qucs, XSPICE, Xyce, NgSPICE, LTSpice, and OPUS [4-11]. They all utilize the Spice core, namely the

Newton-Raphson (NR) iterative algorithm with the standard sparse solving method [2], [10], [12] to find the operating points of nonlinear circuits. In this context, a new CAD software, which we called DSPICE is presented for the first time in this paper to simplify the modeling of analog elements and circuits. In particular, the behavioral modeling of systems by DSPICE is based on a revised computing technique involving the Ngspice and specific packages and libraries. DSPICE can account for detailed circuit analyses in the frequency-domain (AC), time-domain (TR), and directcurrent (DC) operating conditions.

DSPICE using Ngspice for circuit simulation, the Ngspice [11][13] is an open-source mixed-level/mixed-signal electronic circuit simulator. It is a successor of the latest stable release of Berkeley SPICE, version 3f.5, which was released in 1993. A small group of maintainers and the user community contribute to the ngspice project by providing new features, enhancements and bug fixes.

2. The graphical user interface of DSPICE

The graphical user interface (GUI) of DSPICE is presented in Fig. 1 [14]. It programmed by Python 3.8 and PyQt5 library.

The objectives of this interface are:

- Drawing circuit by schematic (CAD approach);
- Creating new SPICE models of electrical elements; [15].

Fig. 1 The GUI of DSPICE software

- Creating new symbols for models;
- Modifying parameters
- Simulating the circuit in the selected mode of operation;
- Presenting simulation results in a dedicated waveform editor (plotly).

As shown in Fig. 2 [15], the graphical interface of the editor of symbols includes: (a) the page for drawing analog elements, (b) the page for attaching symbols with a SPICE description model.

In more detail, the creating of a symbol in the editor is based on the following steps:

- Drawing the electrical elements by lines, rectangles,
- ellipse, etc.;
- Adding pins;
- Model type;
- Adding references;
- Adding parameters;
- Joining the symbol with a SPICE model.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 The interface graphic of editor symbols: (a) drawing electric element (b) attaching symbol with description model by SPICE

3. Conclusion

DSPICE is software used for: simplify the modelling of analog elements by Ngspice, design symbols and simulation circuits with useful interface graphic programmed by python language.

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